

1 Modeling water exsolution from a growing and solidifying felsic magma body.

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9

10 Abstract

11 We modelled water exsolution from a growing and crystallizing felsic magma body using a conductive
12 thermal model with simplified physical mechanisms of volatile transport. Magma solidification leads
13 to the release of the water initially dissolved in the melt. Solidification behaviour depends, in turn, on
14 dissolved water content. The water is channelled where the magma is solidified enough to form a
15 crystal network and rapidly ascends until it encounters solid rock or liquid-rich magma. The rate of
16 water exsolution depends on the basal magma emplacement rate, the cooling rate, and the magma
17 initial water content. Water-rich layers form and are eventually trapped in the solid rock as cooling
18 and crystallization proceeds. We ran our model with a quasi-eutectic granite composition and a non-
19 eutectic monzogranite composition. The non-eutectic magma crystallises on a wider range of
20 temperature than the eutectic magma, produces more mush, and is more prone to the formation of
21 water-rich lenses. Exsolved water accumulates on the sides of the chamber for both tested
22 compositions and also above the top of the chamber for the non-eutectic composition. The actual
23 presence of these water-rich layers in nature and their lifetime depends on whether the water is
24 further released by fracturing. Our results accounts for the observed decoupling of volatiles from

25 magma and for the episodic nature of volcano deformation. It has implications for the interpretation
26 of magma chambers tomography as water-rich lenses would be difficult to distinguish from melt-rich
27 lenses.

28

29 Keywords: magma, volatiles, water exsolution, granite

30

31 1 Introduction

32 Magmas are mixtures of melt, crystals, and volatiles. At depth, they contain various dissolved volatile
33 species, including H₂O, CO₂, and SO₂. Magma decompression or crystallization induces volatiles
34 exsolution and formation of an independent phase of supercritical fluid.

35 Volatiles play an important role in volcanology. Their proportions strongly affect eruptions styles as
36 gas-rich magmas are more explosive and hazardous than their gas-poor counterpart. The presence of
37 exsolved volatiles also affects geophysical measurements. On the one hand, exsolved volatiles
38 increase magma compressibility, so that magma volumes may be underestimated if based on ground
39 surface deformation (Tait et al, 1989). On the other hand, the change in volume caused by water
40 exsolution in closed system induces an overpressure that may lead to the rupture of the chamber
41 walls (Blake, 1984; Fowler and Spera, 2008, 2008; Tait et al., 1989). Volatiles also affect seismic wave
42 velocities and electrical resistivity and make magma chamber imaging difficult to interpret.

43 Volatiles transfer is believed to play a role in petrogenesis (Collins et al., 2020; Weinberg and
44 Hasalová, 2015). The presence of H₂O increases melt fractions. Fluxing of the crust by H₂O exsolved
45 from a magma is expected to promote crustal melting. The long-term influence of volatiles on the
46 fate of magmatic systems is thus not restricted to eruptive processes. Fluxes and concentration of
47 magmatic volatiles are also keys in the generation of ore deposits. Metals present in the magma are

48 partitioned in the supercritical phase and transported by the volatiles towards upper levels above the
49 magma chamber where they precipitate (Richards, 2011).

50 Excess mass of volcanic SO₂ emission suggest that volatiles separate from the magma at depth
51 (Christopher et al., 2015; Wallace, 2001). For this paper, we modeled H₂O exsolution in a growing
52 magma body in relation to magma cooling and solidification and show volatiles decoupling from
53 magma. We tested the influence of magma chamber growth rate and magma composition, including
54 initial water content, on exsolved volatile spatial and temporal distributions. At magmatic pressures
55 and temperatures, the exsolved volatiles are supercritical fluids; for simplicity, we still use the terms
56 bubbles and foam. We will also use the term water independently of its state.

57

58 2 Numerical models

59 2.1 Magma chamber growth

60 We model the growth of a magma chamber by under-accretion of sills. This growth geometry is
61 supported by field observations (Grocott et al., 2009; Michel et al., 2008), geophysics (Cruden and
62 McCaffrey, 2001), and laboratory experiments (Kavanagh et al., 2006; Menand, 2011). The presence
63 and size of a magma chamber, which we define here as a body of magma with a melt fraction above
64 about 0.5 and that is larger than a single sill, depends on the magma body growth rate (Annen,
65 2009). This growth rate is the thickness of sills divided by the time interval between sill
66 emplacements (rest interval). It is equivalent to the flux divided by footprint area that is commonly
67 used in the literature (Sliwinski et al., 2019). If emplaced in a cold crust and if the growth rate is low
68 enough, the first sills completely solidify during the rest interval. With each sill intrusion, heat is
69 transferred to the surroundings and the temperatures of the whole system increase. When
70 temperatures are high enough, melt subsists in the sills during the rest interval, and with each new
71 emplaced sill magmas accumulate. We call incubation time the moment when magma starts to

72 accumulate. Both the incubation time and the size reached by the magma chamber depend on the
73 emplacement rate. We did not consider mechanical effects on the stability or growth of the chamber
74 and did not allow the country rock to partially melt (Karlstrom et al., 2010). More details on the heat
75 transfer model we used can be found in Annen et al. (2008) and Annen (2009).

76 For the present paper, the exsolution and transfer of water was implemented in the simulation of
77 magma chamber growth. H₂O fractions, melt fractions, and temperatures are calculated both during
78 the growth and the solidification of the magma body. The magma body grows until the total
79 thickness of intruded material reaches 2000 m, after which new sill injections no longer occur. The
80 horizontal extent of the sills is also 2000 m. The simulation continues to run until no melt remains in
81 the system. We also simulated the cooling of a 2000 m thick, 2000 m wide magma body that was
82 instantaneously emplaced. The final geometry and volume of the intrusive body is similar for all
83 simulations.

84 The simulations are run in 2D on a square grid with cylindrical coordinates. Sills have a cylindrical
85 geometry and pile up to build a cylindrical composite intrusion, the final shape of which is
86 axisymmetric and isometric. The volume of each new sill is accommodated by moving downwards
87 the material below the sill. It is an approximation of magma accommodation by chamber floor
88 subsidence (Cruden and McCaffrey, 2001). The finite difference formulation of the heat equation is
89 used to calculate temperature:

90

$$91 \quad \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = \kappa \nabla^2 T \quad (1)$$

92

$$93 \quad H = \rho c T + \rho X_m L \quad (2)$$

94

95 With κ the thermal conductivity, ρ the density, c the specific heat, T the temperature, X_m the melt
96 mass fraction, and L the latent heat of crystallisation. The list of symbols is in Table 1. Details of the
97 discretization by finite difference of the equations can be found in Annen et al (2008). The thermal
98 conductivity κ depends on temperature and on the lithostatic pressure (Chapman and Furlong,
99 1992):

$$100 \quad \kappa = \kappa_0 \frac{1+1.5 \times 10^{-6} z}{1+1 \times 10^{-4} T} \quad (3)$$

101 where κ_0 is the thermal conductivity at surface temperature and pressure, and z is depth.

102

103 2.2 Volatile exsolution

104 We assume that exsolution due to decompression during ascent has occurred before magma
105 emplacement. According to Duan (2014), in silicic melts, all CO_2 might be already lost before H_2O
106 starts to exsolve. In this paper, we specifically address the exsolution rate of water as the main
107 volatile phase in magmas emplaced in the upper crust. The solubility of water, C_w , is only weakly
108 influenced by temperature and composition (Duan, 2014). It is mainly a function of pressure P
109 (Newman and Lowenstern, 2002; Schöpa et al., 2017; Sparks, 1978; Tait et al., 1989):

110

$$111 \quad C_w = sP^n \quad (4)$$

112

113 with $s = 4.11 \times 10^{-6} \text{ Pa}^{-n}$, and $n = 0.5$ (Burnham and Jahns, 1962).

114

115 If a magma is undersaturated, dissolved H_2O concentrates in the melt while the magma cools and
116 crystallizes:

117

118
$$X_d = \frac{X_0 - X_c}{X_m} \quad (5)$$

119

120 where X_d is the weight fraction of H₂O dissolved in the melt, X_0 is the initial weight fraction of water
121 dissolved in magma, X_c is the fraction of H₂O that enters hydrous minerals, and X_m is the weight
122 fraction of melt. When X_d exceeds C_w , water is exsolved.

123 *Melt fractions*

124 We based our relationship between melt fractions, dissolved water content, and temperatures on
125 the experimental data of Whitney (1988) that were obtained at a pressure of 2 kbar. At this pressure,
126 the solubility of water is about 6 wt%. The relationship between melt fractions and temperatures
127 depends on the melt water content (Whitney, 1988). If the water exsolved during crystallization does
128 not remain in the magma or mush, any reheating consecutive to the emplacement of a new batch of
129 magma produces a melt that is undersaturated in water and the melt fraction is lower than it was
130 originally at the same temperature (Caricchi and Blundy, 2015). This effect is for the first time
131 integrated in a numerical simulation, which allows us to estimate the error induced by neglecting the
132 effect of water loss when modelling incrementally growing magma bodies.

133 Figure 1 shows the relationships between melt fraction and temperature used in the numerical
134 simulation. To build figure 1a, we used the experimental data of Whitney (1988) for Cape Ann granite
135 (Massachussets). The liquidus temperatures for different water content were estimated from
136 Whitney's figure 2b (Whitney, 1988). For water-undersaturated compositions, the relationship
137 between liquidus temperature T_l and magma water content X_0 is close to linear, so that in the
138 numerical simulation (fig 1):

139

140
$$T_l = -4300X_0 + 1200 \quad (6)$$

141

142 The melt fraction-temperature curve for a saturated composition (6 wt% H₂O) is obtained by linearly
143 interpolating between experimental data points. For magmas that are undersaturated at liquidus,
144 saturation is reached at melt fraction $X_{ms} = (X_0 - X_c)/0.06$. The temperature T_{sat} corresponding to X_{ms} is
145 read on the saturation curve. The undersaturated curves join the saturated curve at this point, and
146 for any lower temperatures the melt fraction is that of a saturated composition (Caricchi and Blundy,
147 2015). To fit Whitney's experiment data with H₂O content of 1, 2, 3, and 5 wt%, we used linear curves
148 that relies T_{sat} with 800 °C and 800 °C with T_l . The melt fraction at 800 °C depends on the water
149 content (Fig 1a). The numerical simulation is valid only with H₂O content X_0 in excess of the amount
150 of water trapped in crystal X_c . The results are presented for $X_c = 0.4$ wt%, which corresponds to the
151 crystallization of about 10 wt% biotite. For all water contents between 0.4 wt% ($=X_c$) and 6 wt%
152 (saturation), $X_m(T=800^\circ\text{C})$ is found by interpolation.

153 To test the effect of the magma composition, we simulated the injection of a water-saturated and a
154 water under-saturated Cape Ann magma. We also ran simulations with the melt fraction-
155 temperature relationship obtained with Rhyolite-MELTS for the Mt. Capanne monzogranite
156 composition (Barboni et al., 2015 and fig. 1b). In this last composition, we neglect the effect of H₂O
157 loss on the melt fraction-temperature curve. We will show a posteriori using the Cape Ann granite
158 curves that this effect is insignificant. In comparison with the Cape Ann granite curve, the Mt.
159 Capanne curve is less steep at low temperature and the mush state, where crystals form a network
160 and can channel water, covers a wider range of temperatures. The initial temperature of the magma
161 at the time of emplacement is that of the liquidus and the magma is crystal-free. Mt Capanne
162 composition has a higher liquidus temperature than the Cape-Ann composition so it advects more
163 heat into the system.

164 2.3 Volatiles transport

165 When saturation is exceeded, bubbles form. Their fate depends on the crystal and volatile fractions.
166 In contrast to other models (e.g. Black and Manga, 2016), the bubbles in our model do not rise in the

167 liquid magma, but in the mush only. More precisely, for gas fraction < 0.5 and crystal volume fraction
168 < 0.4 , individual bubbles rise independently (Parmigiani et al, 2017), and their velocity v is controlled
169 by Stokes law. The presence of other bubbles and of suspended crystals hinder bubble ascent and
170 decrease their velocity. At 2 kbar, bubble diameters are typically a few tens of μm (Lyakhovsky et al.,
171 1996). Figure 2 shows the rise velocity for 50- μm -diameter bubbles and a melt viscosity of 10^5 Pa s .
172 The bubble velocity is of the order of mm per year. Considering the very slow rise of the bubbles, we
173 followed Parmigiani et al (2017) in assuming that the exsolved water is immobile and remains in the
174 magma for crystal volume fractions < 0.4 .

175 It has been shown experimentally (Barth et al., 2019; Holtzman et al., 2012; Oppenheimer et al.,
176 2015; Varas et al., 2015) and numerically (Parmigiani et al., 2017) that mushes are favorable to the
177 formation of permeable pathways and gas migration. For crystal volume fractions in the range 0.4-
178 0.7, crystals form a connected network with gas and melt confined in the interstitial space. At gas
179 volume fraction between a critical value ε_{cr}^g and 0.5, gas viscous fingering occurs. Fingering channels
180 allows the upwards migration of the gas through the interstitial melt within the crystal network. ε_{cr}^g
181 was determined through numerical simulations by Parmigiani et al (2017):

182

$$183 \quad \varepsilon_{cr}^g = 2.75\varepsilon_c^3 - 2.79\varepsilon_c^2 + 0.63\varepsilon_c + 0.1 \quad (7)$$

184

185 The velocity of exsolved volatiles transported through channeling is on the order of a few mm to a
186 few cm per seconds (Parmigiani et al., (2017)). So the time needed to cross any reasonable thickness
187 of mush is much shorter than the numerical time step of the simulation, which is 5 yrs for a cell
188 dimension of 25 m. At the scale of our simulation, we consider that degassing and transport through
189 channel are instantaneous. At each time step, the water exsolved in an area of magma reservoir
190 where the crystal volume fraction is between 0.4 and 0.7 and the volatile volume fraction is between

191 ε_{cr}^g and 0.5 is transported vertically upwards until it hits a domain where these conditions are not
192 fulfilled.

193

194 3 Results

195 3.1 Distribution of exsolved H₂O

196 In the simulation, the exsolved water accumulates at the interface between mush and liquid magma
197 ($\varepsilon_c < 0.4$) and at the interface between mush and solid ($\varepsilon_c > 0.7$). Figures 3 and 4 show how the exsolved
198 water volume fraction and the crystal weight fraction evolve during magma chamber formation and
199 solidification. For an igneous body growing by accretion of sills, the first sills completely solidify
200 between two magma injections, and water can only be transported over the thickness of a single sill.
201 Water concentrations underline the shape of these first sills (fig 3a-d, fig 4 a-d, and fig 5d). After an
202 incubation period that depends on the sill emplacement rate, a magma chamber forms (figs. 3 e-h
203 and 4 e-h). Channeling and water accumulation happen where the chamber cools down and the
204 magma turns into a mush. Magma chambers form later when the sill emplacement rate is low
205 (Annen, 2009). In the limiting case where the emplacement rate is too low for a magma chamber to
206 form at all over the duration of the simulation, the concentration of water is limited by the size of the
207 sills (fig 5 g-i).

208 At higher injection rates, the final volatile distribution is an integration of the pre- and post-
209 emplacement evolutions. Post emplacement, as it cools down, the magma chamber is surrounded by
210 a corona of mush propitious to gas channeling. As detailed below, the thickness of this mush
211 envelope depends on magma composition (compare fig 3e-h and fig 4e-h). The concentration of
212 water is maximum atop the mush column. The thicker is the mush, the more water is channeled
213 upwards. The thickest mush columns are at the outer periphery of the axisymmetric magma
214 chamber. So exsolved water preferentially accumulates on the upper side of the chamber. The locus

215 of maximum water concentration moves inwards as the magma chamber retracts by cooling, which
216 leaves behind trails of high water concentration (fig 5a, d). As the chamber solidifies, water-rich
217 pockets and layers get trapped in the solidified granite while the mush is water depleted.

218 3.2 Magma composition

219 Magma composition and volatile content affect the slopes of the melt fraction-temperature curve
220 (fig 1). The Cape Ann granite water-saturated composition evolves along a steeper melt fraction-
221 temperature slope than an undersaturated granite composition or the Mt. Capanne monzogranite
222 composition. As a result, the envelope of mush around the quasi-eutectic magma chamber (Fig. 3) is
223 narrower than that around the non-eutectic chambers (Fig. 4).

224 Figure 6 shows in more detail how the volume fraction of crystals, melt, and water — before any
225 water transport — evolve with temperature. It also shows the critical gas fraction. Although granitic
226 undersaturated compositions produce more mush than a saturated composition (fig. 1), less volatile
227 transport occurs through them because volatiles saturate and exsolve at lower temperature and
228 higher crystallinity compared to saturated compositions (Figure 6b and 7). For the Cape Ann
229 composition with 2 wt% initial water, no volatile transport and accumulation occur (fig. 6c and 7c).
230 The water exsolves at a melt fraction (0.27 wt%) that is below the critical value for channeling (fig.
231 6c) and the bubbles remain trapped in the crystal-rich material. The Mt. Capanne monzogranite,
232 water-saturated composition fosters the most transport and accumulation of volatiles (fig 7d). A
233 channel-prone mush is present between solidus and about 800 °C and the gas proportion is above
234 the critical fraction in this temperature range (fig 6d). At the end of the solidification stage (26,000
235 yrs on fig.3), a body of mush without liquid core is present for this composition. At this stage, most
236 water concentration occurs within and atop the mush body (Fig. 4f).

237

238 3.3 Volatiles output rates

239 Figure 8 shows the cumulated mass of H₂O exsolved that is assumed extractable because not trapped
240 in the liquid magma. The water fluxes reflect the magma fluxes, i.e. they depend on the sill
241 emplacement rate and radius (fig. 8a). The radius is the most important parameter since it controls
242 both the amount of magma and water available and the cooling surface area. As expected, the
243 exsolution rate is lowest for an undersaturated magma (Figure 8b). The saturated, Mt. Capanne
244 monzogranite produces exsolved volatiles at a slightly higher rate than the Cape Ann saturated
245 granite (fig 8b).

246

247 3.4 Effect of water loss on melt fractions

248 The effect of water loss on the evolution of melt fractions for the water-saturated Cape Ann granite
249 was tested by comparing the results from runs where the melting curve was readjusted to the new
250 conditions in cells that previously lost water and the magma became under-saturated upon
251 remelting, with runs where water loss or gain has no effect on the melting curves. In the second case,
252 only the saturation curve (blue upper curve in fig. 1a) was used in the computation of melt fractions
253 independently of the actual melt water content.

254 Water loss has no effect on melt fraction for an instantaneously emplaced body that is only cooling
255 because there is no reheating and remelting of partially solidified magma. Since only the water that
256 is in excess of saturation is exsolved, the melt stays saturated and remains on the saturation curve.

257 For an incrementally growing body, the water loss effect on melt fractions is not null but is very
258 weak. Reheating and remelting of former sills by new ones is limited. Figure 9 shows the difference in
259 melt wt% between the two simulations. In the case shown here, i. e. for an emplacement rate of one
260 100 m thick sill every 1000 yrs, neglecting the effect of water results in a maximum melt fraction
261 overestimation of 3 wt% at the outer boundary of the mush and an underestimation of less than 1

262 wt% melt at the bottom of the chamber. Overall, the difference does not exceed 4% of the total melt
263 volume in the system.

264

265 4 Discussion

266 The simulations presented in this paper provide new insights on what might happen in a growing and
267 solidifying magma chamber. A series of processes, however, have been neglected and can be the
268 focus of further studies.

269 4.1 Volatiles channeling

270 When considering volatile transport through channeling, we neglected the capillary effect, which
271 causes a small fraction of gas to remain within the channels. The amount of gas retained depends on
272 grain sizes and interfacial tensions between crystals and melt, which cannot easily be constrained
273 (Edmonds and Woods, 2018) more precisely than stating that it is much smaller than ε_{cr}^g (6–10
274 vol.%).

275 In our simple model, volatiles only move upwards and not sideways (e.g. Belien et al., 2010), which
276 constrain their level of accumulation to the top of the mush columns they are issued from. The
277 accumulation of volatiles is stopped when their proportion reach 50 vol%, which results in volatile
278 layering. In the real world, we expect further volatile transfer by capillary fracturing, which would
279 result in volatile layers connection and further volatile transport toward the surface.

280 Since the volatiles accumulate atop the mush, the actual distribution of the volatiles depends on the
281 geometry of the magma body. We adopted a simple geometry where the magma chamber regularly
282 grows by under-accretion of sills of similar dimensions. We expect real intrusions to be more
283 irregular and to cause different patterns of volatiles depletion and accumulation.

284 4.2 Magma convection

285 We neglected the possibility that the volatiles that accumulate at the base of the liquid magma
286 chamber might be entrained in the chamber by magma convection. Magma convection is not
287 included in our model and the cooling rates might be underestimated. Scaling of magma convection
288 usually assumes that the magma is heated from below or cooled from above (Worster et al., 1990),
289 whereas in our model and in nature, an intrusion of magma is cooled from both surfaces. In such
290 case, scaling relationships linking thermal gradient, fluid viscosity, and the effects of thermal
291 expansion to a characteristic convection velocity are generally limited to the boundary layer region
292 (e.g. Huber et al., 2009). Estimating the rate of bubble redistribution across the convecting magma
293 without solving for convection itself is thus a complex task. Our results suggest that neglecting
294 volatile entrainment by magma convection is of little consequence because volatile accumulation at
295 the base of the magma that would be subject to convective motions, although present, is limited
296 compared to the accumulation at the sides (granite and monzogranite compositions) and atop the
297 chamber (monzogranite composition).

298 4.3 Pressure of exsolved volatile

299 We do not take into account the effect of pressure change due to volatile exsolution on the phase
300 relationship. Indeed, the increase in pressure due to water exsolution is expected to modify water
301 solubility (Blake, 1984) until the system reaches a new pressure equilibrium (Tait et al., 1989). Taking
302 these feedback effects into account significantly increases the complexity of the simulations and is
303 beyond the scope of this paper. However, this effect is probably small as the change in pressure that
304 does not lead to chamber fracturing (<10 MPa, Boichu et al., 2008) is smaller than the pressure
305 difference between the top and the base of our chambers at 20 ka (~25 MPa).

306 4.4 Implications for natural systems

307 Our simulations produce a decoupling between volatiles and magma, a process that had been
308 inferred from the imbalance between the excess mass of SO₂ released by volcanoes and the mass of

309 erupted melt (Christopher et al., 2015; Wallace and Gerlach, 1994). However, in contrast with most
310 conceptual models (e.g. Richards, 2011; Wallace, 2001), in our simulations bubbles are channeled by
311 the mush instead of ascending in the liquid magma. The consequence is that accumulation of water
312 occurs at the top of the mush and in the solidified magma rather than atop the liquid-rich magma
313 chamber.

314 Pegmatites, hydrothermal veins, and drusy cavities testify to the presence of water in granites
315 (Bartley et al., 2020). Exhumed granites have lost their water and it remains to be determined if this
316 loss is continuous, i.e. if capillary fracturing and water transport in the solid rock are
317 contemporaneous with exsolution and channeling through the mush. Indeed, any capillary fracturing
318 and further water loss must be delayed for the water-rich layers generated in our numerical
319 simulation to actually form in real intrusive bodies.

320 The possible presence of water-rich layers in magmatic bodies has a series of implications. Water and
321 melt both reduce rock electrical resistivity, density, and seismic wave velocity. Thus, the presence of
322 water in the solidified part of a magma body would affect the interpretation of tomography based on
323 those physical properties and, if not taken into account, would lead to an overestimation of magma
324 chamber dimensions.

325 High proportion of water results in the fragmentation and fluidization of the rock even at low melt
326 fraction (Fowler and Spera, 2008). We speculate that it might play a role in the formation of schlieren
327 structures (Ardill et al., 2020). In case of chamber failure and eruption, the entrainment of those
328 fragmented layers from the roof could explain the common presence of older crystals and the
329 evidence for cold storage in volcanic product (Cooper and Kent, 2014; Rubin et al., 2017).

330 It has been argued that the overpressure due to volatile exsolution is high enough to fracture the
331 wall rocks and trigger eruptions (Blake, 1984; Fowler and Spera, 2008; Tait et al., 1989; Tramontano
332 et al., 2017). The pressure in the chamber depends on the chamber geometry and dimensions, on
333 the magma compressibility, and on the wallrock viscoelastic properties (Jellinek and DePaolo, 2003).

334 In our simulations, those parameters would vary in time and there are gradients in phase proportion,
335 hence in viscosity and compressibility. Computing pressures is beyond the scope of this paper. We
336 note however that in a viscoelastic crust, the pressure is controlled by the rate of volume increase
337 (Jellinek and DePaolo, 2003). This rate is slow since volatile exsolution is controlled by heat diffusion.
338 This aspect was not taken into account in former studies, thus it remains to be shown if bubble
339 exsolution can trigger eruption in a viscoelastic crust.

340 The flux of water released from our modeled magma is of the order 10^7 - 10^8 kg per year. Comparing
341 the flux of water from our simulations with field data is not straightforward. Data on water release
342 from volcanic areas are scarce. The water flux is controlled both by the quantity of magma and by its
343 cooling rate, hence on the cooling area. With radius of 1 to 2 km, the modeled magma bodies are
344 relatively small. With a radius of several tens of kilometers, the cooling surface area would be
345 multiplied by 100 and the exsolution rate would also increase by orders of magnitude. The
346 deformation recorded in the Phlegrean Fields (Italy) between 1982 and 1984 has been linked to the
347 crystallization of 0.83 km^3 of magma and the release of $\sim 6.2 \times 10^{10}$ kg of H_2O (Bodnar et al., 2007).
348 According to Bodnar et al (2007), this water may have been trapped beneath an impermeable layer
349 before being suddenly released when this layer was breached. More generally, ground deformation
350 is often episodic and the volcanoes are said to be breathing. The source of the deformation is
351 attributed to magma (Battaglia et al., 1999; Parks et al., 2012) or to volatiles transport (Bodnar et al.,
352 2007; Vargas et al., 2017). If volatiles are involved, the episodic aspect of deformation suggests that
353 water is able to accumulate before being released by fracturing events (Christopher et al., 2015).

354 Conceptual models for the generation of porphyry copper deposits involve metal transport through
355 volatiles-rich dykes originating from the top of a magma chamber (see Fig. 7 in Richards, 2011). If, as
356 our simulations suggest, water accumulates preferentially at the chamber sides and if it plays a role
357 in the initiation of dykes, we expect volatiles-rich dykes to be initiated from the sides of the chamber.
358 Interestingly, on a reconstruction of the Yerington batholith based on field exposure, the source of
359 the dykes associated with mineralization originates mostly from the side of the granite body (see

360 Fig.1 in Schöpa et al., 2017). Whether this match of locations is fortuitous or not warrants further
361 investigation.

362 Since water-undersaturated Cape Ann granite produces less melt than when it is saturated, Caricchi
363 and Blundy (2015) argue that the effect of water loss needs to be taken into account in modeling of
364 incremental magma emplacement. Our results shed a different light on this issue as they show that,
365 in case of incremental emplacement with injection of a magma of Cape Ann granite composition, the
366 effect of water loss on melt production is not significant. This is because re-melting of previously
367 emplaced sills is limited. Indeed, if the preceding sill is already cold, reheating by the new sill is not
368 enough for the cold sill to reach solidus. If the preceding sill is still hot, i.e. above about 700°C, it has
369 not lost its water by the time the new sill is emplaced and its melting curve remains identical. The
370 situation might be different if the new magma is of different composition and much hotter than the
371 resident magma.

372 5 Conclusions

373 We simulated volatile exsolution and transport within a growing and solidifying magma body.
374 Transport of water through the mush results in an efficient decoupling of water and magma. Our
375 simulations suggest that the geometry and size of the mush that surrounds a magma chamber
376 controls volatiles transfer and accumulation. If the water does not escape immediately through solid
377 rock fracturing, water-rich pockets get trapped in the roof and walls of the intrusive body upon
378 solidification. Magma compositions that are water-saturated but non-eutectic are most susceptible
379 to transfer, concentrate, and eventually expel water compared to eutectic compositions. In contrast,
380 if the magma is strongly under-saturated, water exsolves when the crystal content is already high
381 and cannot move upwards and accumulate.

382 The accumulation and eventual sudden release of water could explain the episodic deformation of
383 volcanoes. The possible presence of water-rich layers in the solidified roof and wall of a magma

384 chamber could lead to an overestimation of the magma reservoir size if not taken into account when
385 interpreting magma chamber tomography.

386 If bubbles play a role in the rupture of a magma reservoir and the initiation of dykes, our result that
387 water accumulates atop the mush rather than atop the liquid magma might explain why many
388 erupted magmas are crystal rich.

389

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393

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532

533 Figure captions

534 Figure 1: Relationships between melt fractions (wt%) and temperatures. (a) Cape Ann granite
535 composition (Whitney, 1988). The relationship varies with water content. The symbols show the
536 positions of experiment data points from (Whitney, 1988). (b) Mt. Capanne monzogranite
537 composition saturated with water (modified from Barboni et al., 2015).

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539 Figure 2: Ascent velocity of gas bubbles as a function of crystal fraction. The velocity is calculated
540 with equations B4 to B6 in Parmigiani et al (2017). The bubbles radius is 50 μm . The gas fraction is
541 calculated as a function of crystal fraction with eq. 5 assuming a saturated composition.

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543 Figure3: Snapshots of magma chamber formation and solidification. Upper row: Exsolved water
544 volume fraction; Lower row: crystal wt fraction relative to melt. 100-m sills are emplaced every 1000
545 yrs during 20,000 yrs. After 20,000 yrs, temperatures relax and the magma chamber boundaries
546 contract. The composition is Cape Ann granite (Whitney, 1988) initially saturated in H₂O.

547

548 Figure 4: As figure 3 for a water-saturated monzogranite (Barboni et al., 2015).

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550 Figure 5: Exsolved water in wt% at the end of simulations. The composition is Cape Ann granite
551 (Whitney, 1988) and was initially saturated with 6 wt% water. Half-domain cross sections are shown
552 on the left; vertical profiles of water contents close to the igneous body central axis are shown in the
553 middle; vertical profiles of water contents close to the igneous body outer edge are shown on the
554 right. (a) (b) (c): The magma chamber was instantaneously emplaced. (d) (e) (f): 100-m sills were
555 emplaced every 1000 years. (g) (h) (i): 100-m sills were emplaced every 10,000 yrs.

556

557 Figure 6: Proportions of crystals, melts, and exsolved volatiles before transport as a function of
558 temperature. (a) a saturated Cape Ann granite, (b) Cape Ann granite with 4 wt% H₂O, (c) Cape Ann
559 granite with 2 wt% H₂O, (d) a saturated Mte Capanne monzogranite. The grey area shows the
560 temperature range over which transport through channels happens, i.e. where the volatile curve is
561 above the critical volatile fraction and the crystal fraction is between 0.4 and 0.7. No transport occurs
562 for the granite with 2 wt% H₂O (c), because the proportion of exsolved volatiles never exceeds the
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565 Figure 7: Snapshots of exsolved water volume fraction. In these simulations, 100-m sills were
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570 fraction isolines and delimit the areas where water is transported through channels. These areas are
571 very thin in (a) and (b). In (c), there is no magma with crystal fraction below 40 vol%. (e) and (f) are
572 enlargement of (a) and (d), respectively.

573

574 Figure 8: Cumulated mass of exsolved water available as a function of time. We assume that the
575 volatiles in suspension as bubbles in the liquid magma are unavailable and are excluded from the
576 calculation. (a) Exsolved water for different emplacement rates and sills radii corresponding to
577 magma fluxes of 0.3 km³/yr for 1 km radius and 0.1 m/yr emplacement, 0.03 km³/yr for 1 km radius
578 and 0.01 m/yr emplacement, and 1.26 km³/yr for 2 km radius and 0.1 m/yr emplacement. The
579 composition is Cape Ann water-saturated granite. (b) Exsolved water for different compositions of
580 magma emplaced at the same rate of 0.01 m/yr and same sill radius of 1 km. The total and final mass
581 of water exsolved is shown by the horizontal dashed lines.

582

583 Figure 9: Effect of water loss on melt fractions. The colors show the difference in melt mass fractions
584 in wt% between a model that takes into account water loss and a model that neglects the effect of
585 water loss on the melting curves. The composition is water-saturated Cape Ann granite. 100-m sills
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